

Ascending and Descending Orders of Annamalai's Binomial Coefficient

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Abstract: This paper presents the analysis of ascending and descending orders with Annamalai's binomial coefficient compared with traditional combination of combinatorics. This will help us to understand how to use and compute the binomial coefficient in problems-solving in the field of combinatorics and discrete mathematics including geometric series and binomial expansion.

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1. Introduction

Let N be the set of natural numbers including zero. Annamalai's Binomial Coefficient [1-9] is

$$V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\cdots(r+n)}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{r+i}{n!} V_n^r \quad (n \geq 1, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N),$$

where $V_n^0 = V_0^n$ and $V_0^n = 1$.

The comparison between Annamalai's binomial coefficient and traditional combination of combinatorics are given below:

$V_x^y = V_y^x$ denotes the optimized combination. Let $z = x + y$. Then, $zC_x = zC_y$.

Also, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = \frac{n!}{n!0!} = 1$ and $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$ ($\because 0! = 1$).

Note that both V_r^n and nC_r are not equal.

2. Ascending and Descending Orders

If n is a positive even integer and $n > r$, the ascending and descending order is

$$V_0^n < V_1^{n-1} < V_2^{n-2} < \cdots < V_{\frac{n}{2}-2}^{\frac{n}{2}+2} < V_{\frac{n}{2}-1}^{\frac{n}{2}+1} < V_{\frac{n}{2}}^{\frac{n}{2}} > V_{\frac{n}{2}+1}^{\frac{n}{2}-1} > V_{\frac{n}{2}+2}^{\frac{n}{2}-2} > \cdots > V_{n-2}^2 > V_{n-1}^1 > V_n^0,$$

For example,

$$V_0^{10} < V_1^9 < V_2^8 < V_3^7 < V_4^6 < V_5^5 > V_6^4 > V_7^3 > V_8^2 > V_9^1 > V_{10}^0.$$

Simplifying for $n = 10$:

$$V_{\frac{n}{2}}^n = V_{\frac{10}{2}}^{\frac{10}{2}} = V_5^5 = 252 \text{ (highest value) and } V_0^{10} = V_{10}^0 = 1 \text{ (lowest value).}$$

If n is a positive odd integer and $n > r$, the ascending and descending order is

$$V_0^n < V_1^{n-1} < V_2^{n-2} < \dots < V_{\frac{n-2}{2}}^{\frac{n+2}{2}} < V_{\frac{n-1}{2}}^{\frac{n+1}{2}} = V_{\frac{n+1}{2}}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} > V_{\frac{n+2}{2}}^{\frac{n-2}{2}} > \dots > V_{n-2}^2 > V_{n-1}^1 > V_n^0.$$

For example,

$$V_0^9 < V_1^8 < V_2^7 < V_3^6 < V_4^5 = V_5^4 > V_6^3 > V_7^2 > V_8^1 > V_9^0.$$

Simplifying for $n = 9$:

$$V_{\frac{n-1}{2}}^{\frac{n+1}{2}} = V_{\frac{9-1}{2}}^{\frac{9+1}{2}} = V_4^5 = 126 \text{ and } V_{\frac{n+1}{2}}^{\frac{n-1}{2}} = V_5^4 = 126$$

In general, Annamalai's binomial coefficients are in ascending order as follows:

$$V_0^n < V_1^n < V_2^n < V_3^n < \dots < V_{i-1}^n < V_i^n < V_{i+1}^n < \dots < V_{r-1}^n < V_n^n \quad (i, r, n \in N).$$

The following binomial expansion [1-9], binomial series, and binomial distribution [8] are the applications of Annamalai's binomial coefficient.

$$\text{Binomial expansion: } \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^n x^i = \sum_{i=0}^r \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{i+j}{r!} x^i.$$

$$\text{Binomial series: } (x+y)^n = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} x^{n-i} y^i.$$

$$\text{Binomial distribution: } P(x) = V_x^{n-x} p^x q^{n-x},$$

where P = binomial probability, x = number of times for a specific outcome within n trials, p = probability of success on a single trial, q = probability of failure on a single trial, n = number of trials, and $p + q = 1$.

3. Conclusion

This article provides the ascending and descending orders of Annamalai's binomial coefficient that has been compared with traditional coefficient (combination). This will help us to understand how to use and compute the binomial coefficient in problems-solving in the field of combinatorics and discrete mathematics including geometric series [10] and binomial expansion.

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